

ISic1286

I.Sicily inscription 1286

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific (?)

Material

marble

Object

base

(?)

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates**

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140776

1. [— — —]ΚΑΙCΙ [— — — —]

2. [— — —]ΗΤΑΡCΤ [— — —]

3. [— —]ισταμένη Υ [— — —]

4. [— —]Ἄυ[ξ]έντιον [— —]

5. [— —]ΚΗΝΔΙΚΛΕ [— — —]

6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492891

EDCS 39101655

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Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0462 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

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